

Entry No.	Name	Species	Time point for RNA sampling and total raw PE reads (10 ⁶)
GMAR024	2005-40/9818	<i>Festulolium</i> spp.	
GMAR026	FL-5V2N 1/03	<i>Festulolium</i> spp.	
GMAR027	FLNHNK08 H.V. Km11	<i>Festulolium</i> spp.	
GMAR028	FLNHNK08 H.V. Km22	<i>Festulolium</i> spp.	
GMAR030	Achilles 1	<i>Festulolium braunii</i> (LMxFP)	
GMAR034	FLB 5-01-23384	<i>Festulolium braunii</i> (LMxFP)	
GMAR040*	HZ3/III 2005	<i>Festulolium braunii</i> (LMxFP)	0% and 1% (44.3)
GMAR043	PERSEUS ZIV 06	<i>Festulolium braunii</i> (LMxFP)	
GMAR052	FPF-5-07-22851	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>festucoid</i>	
GMAR053*	FPF-5-07-22863	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>festucoid</i>	0% and 1% (90.1)
GMAR055*	FPF-5-08-1105	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>festucoid</i>	0% and 1% (89.1)
GMAR059	Korina 1	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>festucoid</i>	
GMAR066	FELINA	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>loloid</i>	
GMAR069*	FLIP-5-05-22810	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>loloid</i>	0% and 1% (98.8)
GMAR072	FPL-05-11-11028	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>loloid</i>	
GMAR076	Lofa 1	<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LMxFA) <i>loloid</i>	

*Accessions selected for RNA-seq analysis.